

E X P E R I M E N T A L

2:4 - Dimethyl - 3 - cyano - 3 - carboxamido-4-amino-5-*o*-chlorobenzyl- Δ^1 -pyrroline (I, R = *o*-Cl-C₆H₄).—To anhydrous ethanol (50 c.c.), saturated at 0° with dry ammonia gas, (α -acetamido- β -*o*-chlorophenyl)-ethylmethyl ketone (10 g.) and ethyl cyanoacetate (10 g.) were added and the mixture was kept in the refrigerator in a well-closed bottle for 96 hours. Removal of ethanol left a solid which was purified by solution in cold dilute HCl and precipitation by a cold dilute NaOH solution. The solid was finally crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles (6 g.), m.p. 209-10°. (Found: C, 58.78; H, 5.47; N, 18.12. C₁₈H₁₇ON₄Cl requires C, 59.11; H, 5.58; N, 18.39 per cent).

The *picrate* was crystallised from ethanol in yellow needles, m.p. 198-200° (decomp.). (Found: N, 18.23. C₁₈H₁₇ON₄Cl.C₆H₃O₇N₃ requires N, 18.37 per cent).

The 4 *acetamido* derivative was obtained by treatment with acetic anhydride in presence of acetic acid, purified by trituration with cold dilute HCl and it was crystallised from glacial acetic acid-ethanol mixture (1:1) in fine colorless needles, m.p. 271-72°. (Found: N, 15.78. C₁₇H₁₉O₂N₄Cl requires N, 16.16 per cent).

The 4-*allylthiocarbamide* derivative was obtained by refluxing for about 6 hours an ethanolic solution of (I, R = *o*-C₆H₄) and a slight excess of allyl isothiocyanate. The solid obtained by removal of ethanol was trituated first with ether and then with cold dilute HCl and was finally crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 183-84°. (Found: N, 17.12; S, 7.56. C₁₀H₁₂ON₂SCl requires N, 17.34; S, 7.93 per cent).

(γ -Methylmercapto- α -acetamido)-propylmethyl Ketone (II).—A mixture of *dl*-methionine (10 g.), acetic anhydride (42 c. c.) and pyridine (20 c.c.) was heated under reflux on a water-bath for 6 hours. Pyridine and the excess of acetic anhydride were removed by steam-distillation and the mixture was cooled in ice and then extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was carefully washed with cold aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution (5%) and then with water and was finally dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Removal of the ether left a heavy, viscous liquid (6.5 g.) which could not be distilled without decomposition, even under reduced pressure. The ketone was characterised as 2:4-*dinitrophenylhydrazone*, which crystallised from ethanol in fine, yellow needles, m.p. 189-90°. (Found: N, 18.85. C₁₄H₁₆O₃N₆S requires N, 18.97 per cent).

2:4-Dimethyl-3-cyano- α -3-carboxamido-4-amino-5-(β -methylmercapto)-ethyl- Δ^1 -pyrroline (I, R = CH₂-S-CH₂).—Using (γ -methylmercapto- α -acetamido)-propylmethyl ketone and proceeding as in the case of (I, R = *o*-Cl-C₆H₄), (I, R = CH₂-S-CH₂) was obtained and crystallised from ethanol in fine, pinkish needles, m.p. 162°. (Found: N, 21.87; S, 12.12. C₁₁H₁₄ON₄S requires N, 22.05; S, 12.59 per cent).

The *picrate* was obtained from ethanolic solution as yellow needles, m.p. 167-68° (Found: N, 20.15. C₁₁H₁₄ON₄S.C₆H₃O₇N₃ requires N, 20.29 per cent).

The 4-*acetamido* derivative was obtained by employing a mixture of acetic anhydride and acetic acid and was crystallised from a mixture of ethanolic-acetic acid mixture (1:1) in colorless needles, m.p. 220°. (Found: N, 18.73. C₁₃H₂₀O₂N₄S requires N, 18.92 per cent).

[α -Acetamido- β -(3-indole)]-ethylmethyl Ketone (III).—A mixture of *dl*-tryptophane (12 g.), acetic anhydride (45 c.c.) and pyridine (32 c.c.) was heated for about 6 hours under reflux on the water-bath in a flask protected from moisture. After steam-distillation the mixture was cooled and extracted with ethyl acetate. The ethyl acetate extract was successively washed with water, cold aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution (5%) and then with water and was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Removal of ethyl acetate left a heavy, viscous, brownish liquid (11.5 g.), which could not be distilled without decomposition, even under reduced pressure. It was characterised as 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, crystallised from ethanol in brown needles, m.p. 265-66° (decomp.). (Found : N, 19.64. $C_{20}H_{20}O_2N_6$ requires N, 19.81 per cent).

The authors are grateful to Dr. U. P. Basu, Director of the Institute, for his interest in this investigation.

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Received September 22, 1955.